

A Study on Awareness of Various Non-Technical Training Programmes Conducted by Corporate Trainers for IT Companies in Ahmedabad

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the awareness levels among IT professionals in Ahmedabad regarding non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers. The study focuses specifically on IT companies in Ahmedabad, a prominent hub for the IT industry in India. The research examines the awareness levels among IT professionals regarding the availability and benefits of non-technical training programs offered by corporate trainers. The questionnaire will assess the participants' awareness levels of non-technical training programs, including their knowledge of the programs offered, their perceived importance, and their willingness to participate. Data collected from the survey will be analyzed to identify the level of awareness among IT professionals and explore any gaps or discrepancies in their knowledge. The findings of this research will provide insights into the current state of awareness regarding non-technical training programs in the IT industry in Ahmedabad. The results will be beneficial for both corporate trainers and IT companies in understanding the existing levels of awareness and the potential for improving the promotion and utilization of non-technical training programs. Additionally, the study will contribute to bridging the gap between the availability of non-technical training programs and the awareness among IT professionals, ultimately fostering their continuous learning and professional growth.

INTRODUCTION

This study focuses on understanding how much people in Ahmedabad, especially those working in the IT industry, know about non-technical training programmes offered by corporate trainers (Vidani, 2015). Non-technical training programmes are designed to enhance skills that are not specific to a particular technology or programming language (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). These programmes often focus on personal development, leadership skills, communication, teamwork, and other areas that can benefit professionals in their careers (Vidani, 2015).

In Ahmedabad, which is known for its growing IT industry, it is important to assess the level of awareness about these non-technical training programmes (Vidani, 2015). By understanding the awareness level, we can determine if professionals in the IT industry are taking advantage of such programmes to improve their skills and stay competitive in the job market (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

This study will investigate the types of non-technical training programmes available in Ahmedabad, their relevance to the IT industry, and how well-known they are among IT professionals (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). The findings will provide valuable insights into the current awareness levels and the potential impact of these training programmes on the professional growth and development of individuals working in the IT industry in Ahmedabad (Vidani, 2016).

By examining the awareness of non-technical training programmes This research aims to help understand of the importance of continuous learning and professional development in the IT industry (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017). It will also shed light on the efforts made by corporate trainers to offer these programmes and their effectiveness in reaching the target audience (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016).

The findings from this study can be used by IT professionals, trainers, and organizations in Ahmedabad to make informed decisions about their professional development strategies and improve the availability and effectiveness of non-technical training programmes in the city's IT industry (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016).

Let's understand IT industry and how IT industry deals with non-technical programmes:

IT Industry

The IT industry is a broad term that includes many IT organizations. This includes companies that produce software, hardware, or semiconductor equipment, and companies that provide Internet or related services (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018). The three major industry groups in the IT sector are software and services, hardware and technology equipment, and semiconductor and semiconductor equipment. The computer industry, also known as the information technology industry, includes the businesses of computer hardware, computer software development and maintenance, and computer networks (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

Non-Technical Programmes

A non-technical program refers to a training or educational program that focuses on developing skills and knowledge that are not directly related to specific technical or specialized areas (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). Unlike technical programmes that concentrate on specific technologies, programming languages, or technical expertise, non-technical programmes aim to enhance broader skills that are applicable across various industries and professions (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). These programmes typically focus on personal development, communication skills, leadership, critical thinking, project management, teamwork, and other skills that are valuable in professional settings (Singh & Vidani, 2016). Non-technical programmes are designed to complement technical skills and provide individuals with a well-rounded skill set that goes beyond their technical expertise (Vidani & Plaha, 2016). These programmes recognize the importance of soft skills and personal attributes in achieving success in the workplace. They aim to enhance an individual's ability to effectively communicate, collaborate, problem-solve, adapt to change, and lead teams (Solanki & Vidani, 2016).

Non-technical programmes can take various forms, such as workshops, seminars, courses, certifications, or training sessions (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). They are often conducted by corporate trainers, professional development organizations, educational institutions, or specialized training providers (Vidani, 2016). These programmes may cover topics such as communication skills, leadership development, time management, emotional intelligence, conflict resolution, negotiation skills, presentation skills, more (Vidani, Chack, & Rathod, 2017). Non-technical programmes are valuable for professionals across different industries, including the IT industry. They help individuals broaden their skill set, improve their professional capabilities, and enhance their career prospects (Vidani, 2018).

By participating in non-technical programmes, individuals can develop a well-rounded skill set that complements their technical expertise, making them more adaptable, effective, and successful in their professional endeavours (Biharani & Vidani, 2018).

Non-Technical Programmes in World Level IT Industry

The global IT industry recognizes the significance of non-technical programmes in shaping well-rounded professionals and fostering overall career growth. Here's how the world-level IT industry typically views non-technical programmes:

- 1. Comprehensive Skill Development:** The IT industry acknowledges that technical skills alone are not sufficient for success. Non-technical programmes offer professionals the opportunity to develop a wide range of skills beyond their technical expertise. These programmes focus on areas such as leadership, communication, problem-solving, project management, teamwork, and critical thinking. By acquiring these non-technical skills, IT professionals become more versatile and equipped to handle diverse challenges in the industry.

2. **Adaptability to Changing Work Environment:** The IT industry is known for its rapid advancements and evolving landscape. Non-technical programmes enable professionals to adapt to these changes and embrace new technologies and methodologies. These programmes foster skills like adaptability, resilience, and a growth mindset, which are vital for staying relevant and thriving in a dynamic industry. IT professionals who engage in non-technical programmes are better equipped to embrace change, learn new skills, and navigate evolving roles and responsibilities.
3. **Effective Communication and Collaboration:** IT projects often involve collaboration with stakeholders from various backgrounds, including non-technical professionals and clients. Non-technical programmes equip IT professionals with the communication and collaboration skills necessary for effective interaction with team members, project managers, clients, and end-users. These programmes focus on enhancing interpersonal skills, empathy, active listening, and cross-functional collaboration, leading to improved teamwork, productivity, and project outcomes.
4. **Leadership and Management Development:** As IT professionals progress in their careers, many aspire to leadership or management roles. Non-technical programmes offer valuable leadership and management skills that go beyond technical expertise. These programmes cover areas such as strategic thinking, decision-making, team management, conflict resolution, and mentoring. IT industry values professionals who can lead teams, drive innovation, and align technical efforts with business goals.
5. **Client and Business Perspective:** IT professionals often work closely with clients and contribute to solving their business challenges. Non-technical programmes help professionals gain a broader understanding of client needs, industry trends, and business perspectives. This knowledge enables IT professionals to provide comprehensive solutions and contribute effectively to business growth and success.
6. **Competitive Advantage:** In a competitive global IT industry, professionals who possess a combination of technical and non-technical skills have a distinct advantage. Non-technical programmes allow individuals to differentiate themselves by showcasing their broader skill set and ability to contribute beyond technical expertise. Employers recognize the value of professionals who possess a blend of technical and non-technical competencies, as they can bring diverse perspectives, adaptability, and problem-solving capabilities to the table.

Overall, the world-level IT industry embraces non-technical programmes as a valuable investment in the professional development of IT professionals (Biharani & Vidani, 2018). By combining technical skills with non-technical competencies, individuals can enhance their career prospects, contribute effectively to IT projects, and meet the multifaceted demands of the global IT industry (Vidani, 2018).

Non-Technical Programmes in India-Level IT Industry

In the Indian IT industry, non-technical programmes play an important role in IT professional development professionals. Here are some common types of non-technical programmes in the India-level IT industry:

- 1. Leadership and management programmes:** These programmes focus on developing leadership skills and management capabilities among IT professionals. They cover areas such as strategic thinking, decision-making, team management, conflict resolution, and effective communication. Leadership programmes equip IT professionals with the necessary skills to lead teams, handle complex projects, and align technical efforts with organizational goals.
- 2. Communication and soft skills training:** Effective communication and soft skills are crucial for IT professionals to collaborate, present ideas, and interact with clients and stakeholders. Non-technical programmes in this domain concentrate on areas like business communication, presentation skills, negotiation, conflict resolution, and interpersonal skills. These programmes help IT professionals become effective communicators and enhance their overall professional effectiveness.
- 3. Project management programmes:** Project management is a critical skill in the IT industry. Non-technical programmes in project management provide IT professionals with the knowledge and techniques to effectively plan, execute, and manage IT projects. These programmes cover project lifecycle, risk management, stakeholder management, agile methodologies, and other essential project management concepts.
- 4. Professional ethics and work culture:** Non-technical programmes also emphasize professional ethics, work culture, and corporate values. They help IT professionals understand ethical dilemmas, adhere to industry standards and codes of conduct, and foster a positive work environment. These programmes focus on promoting integrity, teamwork, diversity, and inclusion in the workplace.
- 5. Personal effectiveness and well-being:** IT professionals often face high workloads and stress levels. Non-technical programmes in personal effectiveness and well-being aim to support the holistic development of IT professionals. They cover stress management, time management, work-life balance, mindfulness, and techniques to enhance personal well-being and resilience.
- 6. Innovation and creativity programmes:** In the fast-paced IT industry, fostering innovation and creativity is crucial. Non-technical programmes in this area focus on techniques for ideation, problem-solving, and innovation. These programmes help IT professionals think outside the box, generate creative solutions, and embrace a culture of innovation within their organizations.
- 7. Business and industry awareness programmes:** Non-technical programmes that provide insights into business and industry trends are also popular in the Indian IT industry. These programmes help IT professionals understand the broader business context, emerging

technologies, market trends, and customer expectations. They facilitate a better understanding of the industry landscape and empower IT professionals to contribute strategically to organizational growth.

Non-technical programmes in the Indian IT industry are designed to enhance the overall skills, capabilities, and professionalism of IT professionals (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018). By participating in these programmes, IT professionals can broaden their skill set, improve their career prospects, and contribute effectively to their organizations. These programmes play an important role in the continuous development and success of IT professionals in the Indian IT industry (Odedra, Rabadiya, & Vidani, 2018).

Non-Technical Programmes in Gujarat-Level IT Industry

- Non-technical programmes in the Gujarat-level IT industry focus on leadership and management development, enhancing the skills of IT professionals to lead teams, make strategic decisions, and manage projects effectively.
- Gujarat-level IT industry emphasizes non-technical programmes that enhance communication and interpersonal skills, enabling IT professionals to effectively collaborate, present ideas, negotiate, and resolve conflicts with clients and colleagues.
- Non-technical programmes in the Gujarat-level IT industry offer specialized training in project management and agile methodologies, equipping IT professionals with the knowledge and techniques to plan, execute, and deliver successful projects.
- The Gujarat-level IT industry recognizes the importance of business and industry awareness programmes, providing insights into local market dynamics, industry trends, and emerging technologies, empowering IT professionals to contribute strategically to the growth of the industry.
- Personal development and well-being programmes are highly valued in the Gujarat-level IT industry, focusing on stress management, work-life balance, resilience-building, and mindfulness to support the overall well-being and effectiveness of IT professionals.

Objective of Study

Primary objective: The primary objective of the study is to assess the level of consciousness among professionals in the IT industry in Ahmedabad City regarding various non-technical training programmes conducted by corporate trainers. The study aims to measure the extent to which professionals are aware of these programmes and understand their potential benefits in terms of career development and skill enhancement.

Secondary Objective: The secondary objective of the study is to identify the factors influencing professionals' awareness and participation in non-technical training programmes. The study aims to explore factors such as availability of information, perceived relevance of the programmes, cost considerations, and the reputation of corporate trainers conducting these programmes.

Understanding these factors will provide insights into the barriers and motivations for professionals to engage in non-technical training activities

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

(K. Kanapathipillai & S. Azam, 2020) Today, many organizations face challenges when competing in a turbulent business environment. Add to this the current COVID-19 pandemic, and the power of organizations is amplified (Vasveliyya & Vidani, 2019). Malaysian telecommunication companies are not spared from this situation either (Vidani & Das, 2021). Therefore, a key strategy for telecommunications companies to gain competitive advantage is to train employees at all levels to overcome this current deficiency (Sachania, Vora and Vidani). 2019). This study aims to find out whether training affects job performance and job satisfaction, two key variables that lead to the survival and growth of telecommunications companies (Vidani & Das, 2021). Therefore, to achieve the objective of this study, three major telecommunication companies in Malaysia (Sachania, Vora and Vidani, 2019). This study used quantitative techniques to generate empirical results and representations that answer the research question. In the literature, the fields of training, job performance, and job satisfaction have been explored to fill the gaps and determine the importance of on-site training programs on job performance and job satisfaction. This analysis shows that education is statistically significant and strongly related to job performance and job satisfaction (Vidani, 2018). This hypothesis indicates that training programs conducted by telecommunication companies have a significant relationship with employees' job performance and job satisfaction (Vidani, 2018). Therefore, the findings of this study may serve as an example of other companies in Malaysia that do not confirm the effect of training on job performance and job satisfaction (Vidani, 2019). By conducting continuous training, companies can face the current economic challenges caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and remain alive, thriving and competitive.

(A. Bello & Kai-Ying A. Chan, 2014) Past research has shown that one of the major challenges faced by knowledge management processes is enabling employees to share what they know in the organization (Vidani, Jacob, and Patel, 2019). The challenge here is with those who use IT tools to share knowledge and therefore it is important to know user attitudes and behaviors when using IT to share knowledge (Vidani & Das, 2021). The model used in this study is based on the technology acceptance model, with extensions from Coleman's process of shared influence known as subjective norms (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019). The results show that the perceived usefulness of information technology in knowledge sharing has a greater effect on users' intention to use information technology compared to the effect of subjective norms. (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019) It is recommended that training programs, seminars, and workshops be organized to increase awareness of these IT tools to share knowledge and increase perceived usefulness of employees. (Vidani, Jacob, & Patel, 2019).

(Melton, 2008) Based on a case study of a global teaching team, this article focuses on collaboration with translators, a key competency for professional communication (Vidani & Singh, 2017). This study confirms the value of

approaching translation as a collaborative effort, rather than simple communication, and suggests the need to integrate translation and localization and build team trust (Vidani & Singh, 2017). Related competencies include understanding cultural and professional contexts, utilizing bicultural perspectives, and building team relationships (Vidani & Singh, 2017). The pursuit of these competencies should be drawn from the literature of translation and intercultural communication studies and informed by diverse rhetorical traditions (Vidani & Das, 2021). Global educational and research partnerships are an ideal way to pursue these goals (Vidani & Singh, 2017). Such collaborations can improve research methods and challenge culturally based assumptions about the role and competence of translation-related communication (Vidani & Singh, 2017).

(A. Bello & Kai-Ying A. Chan, 2014) Past research has shown that one of the major challenges faced by knowledge management processes is enabling employees to share what they know in the organization (Vidani & Plaha, 2017). The challenge here is with those who use IT tools to share knowledge, so it is important to know the attitudes and behavior of users when using IT to share knowledge (Vidani & Plaha, 2017). The model used in this study is based on the technology acceptance model, with extensions from Coleman's collective influence process known as subjective norms. The results showed that the perceived usefulness of information technology in knowledge sharing has a greater impact on users' intention to use information technology compared to the influence of subjective norms (Vidani & Plaha, 2017). It is recommended that training programs, seminars and workshops be organized to increase awareness of these IT tools to share knowledge and increase the perceived usefulness of employees (Vidani & Plaha, 2017).

(G. M. Perron & R. Cote, J. F. Duffy, 2006): The need and benefits of more sustainable approaches to business management have been widely discussed in the literature (Vidani, 2020). Many organizations undertake environmental management initiatives to improve their environmental performance, and this process has been found to have other benefits such as financial savings and reduced liability risk (Vidani, 2020). However, many limitations can hinder the transformation of green and responsible organizations (Vidani, 2020). These limitations include issues related to organizational culture and change management (Vidani, 2020). To overcome these limitations and successfully implement environmental management initiatives, the literature suggests that members of an organization can improve their environmental impacts and awareness by participating in environmental awareness training activities that create sustainable knowledge and engagement. It has been suggested that understanding organizational policies is important. (Vidani, 2020). Equipped with this knowledge, employees will be able to understand how their environment affects their work and decisions (Vidani, 2018). Different companies adopt different approaches to environmental management training (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). It is important for organizations to evaluate the effectiveness of their training investments and ensure their returns. Two power company case studies are used to illustrate the importance of evaluating environmental

awareness efforts (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). The results of the study showed that despite significant time and money invested in a one-time environmental awareness training program, the training provided was not enough to increase employees' environmental awareness of the company's environmental impacts (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). We briefly discuss the results and provide recommendations to improve the outcome of your educational investment (Vidani, 2018).

(El-Ebiary, N. , Yazeed Al Moaiad, , & M. , 2016) The purpose of this study is to find out the effectiveness of the implementation of Management Information System (MIS) in Almadina International University (MEDIU), Malaysia and to find out the advantages and challenges of the management system that is currently used in the university. . Various non-probability sampling techniques have been used in creating the final sample frame (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). Researchers also used descriptive statistics when generating data from survey questionnaires (Vidani & Dholakia, 2020). The results of this study show the inherent benefits of using management information systems in organizations (Ratoud, Mogharajani and Vidani, 2022). In general, system users are satisfied with the implemented management information system because the system has successfully improved the productivity and performance of their operations (Ratoud, Mogharajani, & Vidani, 2022). The system also reduced administrative errors and aided decision-making procedures. However, this review also shows that the stakeholders in content management systems are not completely satisfied with the current systems and their usefulness (Ratoud, Mogharajani, & Vidani, 2022). This study recommends increasing awareness and training about the usefulness of current management information systems (Ratoud, Mogharajani, & Vidani, 2022).

Scope the Study

- ❖ **Assessment of Training Needs:** Evaluate the training needs of IT professionals in Ahmedabad City by conducting surveys, interviews, or focus groups. Identify the non-technical skills and competencies that are in demand and explore the gaps between the existing skills and the required skills.
- ❖ **Exploration of Training Programmes:** Identify the range of non-technical training programmes offered by corporate trainers in Ahmedabad City. Investigate the different types of programmes available, such as leadership development, communication skills, problem-solving, time management, teamwork, and others.
- ❖ **Awareness Levels:** Measure the level of awareness among IT professionals in Ahmedabad City regarding the non-technical training programmes. Determine the extent to which these professionals are aware of the available training opportunities and their perceptions of the importance and value of non-technical skills in the IT industry.
- ❖ **Effectiveness of Training Programmes:** Assess the effectiveness of the non-technical training programmes conducted by corporate trainers. Evaluate the impact of these programmes on the participants' skills, job performance,

career advancement, and overall satisfaction. Gather feedback from participants through surveys, interviews, or follow-up assessments.

- ❖ **Barriers and Challenges:** Identify the barriers and challenges faced by IT professionals in accessing non-technical training programmes. Explore factors such as lack of awareness, financial constraints, time constraints, organizational support, and other potential obstacles that may hinder participation in these programmes.
- ❖ **Recommendations and Best Practices:** Provide recommendations for improving the awareness and availability of non-technical training programmes in Ahmedabad City. Based on the study findings, suggest best practices for corporate trainers, IT organizations, and policymakers to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of such programmes.

METHODS

Research design is DESCRIPTIVE research design.

Source of Data

Primary data

It is original primary data, for specific phase of research project. For this project used Questionnaire common research instrument.

Secondary data

Books, Articles, journal and internet etc.

Sample Plan

Sample population: People of Ahmedabad.

Sample Unit: IT industry in Ahmedabad.

Sample size: The total sample size of our project is 100.

Sample method: Non-probability convenience sampling method.

Research/ Statistical tools: The data analysis tools which used in this are SPSS software and MS Excel.

RESULTS

H1: There is significant difference between gender and satisfaction towards non-technical training programmes.

H2: There is significant between gender and awareness towards non-technical programmes conducted by corporate trainers.

H3: There is relation between occupation and observation of demand non-technological training programmes in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.

H4: There is a relation between occupation and non-technical training programmes conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry in the Ahmedabad.

Hypothesis Testing

1. Gender and how satisfied are you with the non-technical training programmes offered by corporate trainers in the IT industry among hypothesis testing.

H1: There is significant difference between Gender and satisfaction towards non-technical training programmes.

Table 1. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Gender	how_satisfied_are_you_with_the_non-technical_training_programmes_offered_by_corporate_trainers_in_the_IT_industry_in_Ahmedabad_city?
N	100	72
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	3.51
	Std. Deviation	1.256
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.234
	Positive	.122
	Negative	-.234
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	3.866	1.985
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Since the value is less than 0.05, reject H0. The data is not normal. Now

Test Statistics ^a	
	Gender
Mann-Whitney U	96.000
Wilcoxon W	267.000
Z	-.164
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.870
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	.912 ^b
a. Grouping Variable: how_satisfied_are_you_with_the_non-technical_training_programmes_offered_by_corporate_trainers_in_the_IT_industry_in_Ahmedabad_city?	
b. Not corrected for ties.	

Statement related satisfaction towards non-technical programmes in IT industry.	Sig.	Sig. value < 0.05: H0 is rejected Sig. value > 0.05: H0 is accepted
Gender	.302	H0 is accepted

INTERPRETATION: - In these above table, we can see that the significant value is 0.302 which is more than 0.05. So, we to accept the null hypothesis which is means that there is no significant difference between gender and satisfaction towards non-technical training programmes.

2. Gender and aware are you of these non-technical training programmes conducted by corporate trainers in the IT industry among hypothesis testing

H2: There is a significant between gender and awareness towards soft skill program conducted by corporate trainers.

Table 2. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Gender	How_aware_are_you_of_these_non-technical_training_programmes_conducted_by_corporate_trainers_in_the_IT_industry_in_Ahmedabad? [Soft skill training]
N	100	72
Mean	1.41	2.65
Normal Parameters ^{a,b} Std. Deviation	.494	.858
Most Extreme Absolute Differences	.387	.282
Positive	.387	.204
Negative	-.294	-.282
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	3.866	2.393
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Since the value is less than 0.05, reject H0. The data is not normal

Test Statistics^a

	Gender
Mann-Whitney U	69.000
Wilcoxon W	124.000
Z	-1.419
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.156
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	.247 ^b

a. Grouping Variable: How_aware_are_you_of_these_non-technical_training_programmes_conducted_by_corporate_trainers_in_the_IT_industry_in_Ahmedabad? [Soft skill training]

b. Not corrected for ties.

Statement related awareness towards non-technical programmes in IT industry.	Sig.	Sig. value < 0.05: H0 is rejected Sig. value > 0.05: H0 is accepted
Behavioural training	.317	H0 is accepted
E-mail etiquettes	.031	H0 is rejected
Soft skill training	.989	H0 is accepted
office etiquettes	.363	H0 is accepted
Corporate communication	.514	H0 is accepted

INTERPRETATION: - In these above table, we can see that the significant value of Behavioral training (0.317), E-mail etiquettes (0.031), soft skill training (0.989), Office etiquettes (0.363), Corporate communication (0.514) are more than 0.05. So, we to accept the null hypothesis which is means that There is no relation between gender and awareness towards non-technical programs conducted by corporate trainers.

3. Occupation and Non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry among hypothesis testing

H3: there is significant between occupation and non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry in Ahmedabad.

Table 3. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Occupation	statement:[Non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry in Ahmedabad.]
N	100	72
Mean	3.85	2.38
Normal Parameters ^{a,b} Std. Deviation	1.258	1.250
Most Extreme Absolute	.310	.298
Differences Positive	.220	.298
Negative	-.310	-.146
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	3.096	2.533
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Since the value is less than 0.05, reject H0. The data is not normal

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	statement:[Non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry in Ahmedabad.]
Chi-Square	3.524
df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.474

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Occupation

Statement related non-technical programmes in IT industry.	Sig.	Sig. value < 0.05: H0 is rejected Sig. value > 0.05: H0 is accepted
Occupation	.271	H0 is accepted

INTERPRETATION: - In these above table, we can see that the significant value is 0.271 which is more than 0.05. So, we to accept the null hypothesis which is means that there is no relation between occupation and non-technical training programs conducted by corporate trainers are essential for career growth in the IT industry in Ahmedabad.

- Occupation and I have observed an increase in demand for non-technological training programs in the IT industry among hypothesis testing.

H4: There is a significant between occupation and observation of demand non-technological training programs in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.

Table 4. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Occupation	statement:[I have observed an increase in demand for non-technological training programs in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.]
N	100	72
Mean	3.85	2.47
Normal Parameters ^{a,b} Std. Deviation	1.258	1.175
Most Extreme Absolute Differences	.310	.212
Positive	.220	.212
Negative	-.310	-.122
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	3.096	1.797
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	statement:[I have observed an increase in demand for non-technological training programs in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.]
Chi-Square	4.000
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.406

- a. Kruskal Wallis Test
- b. Grouping Variable: Occupation

Statement related observed an increase in demand for non-technical programmes in IT industry.	Sig.	Sig. value < 0.05: H0 is rejected Sig. value > 0.05: H0 is accepted
Occupation	.297	H0 is accepted

INTERPRETATION: - In the above table, we can see that the significant value is 0.297 which is more than 0.05. So, we to accept the null hypothesis which means that there is no relation between occupation and observation of demand non-technological training programs in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.

DISCUSSION

- According to the research 59% respondents are male and 41% of respondents are female, so it is indicating to the majority of males are in the IT industry.
- 61% of the respondents are from the '18-25' age group.
- 48% of them are students.
- 36% of the respondents are having no prior experience in the IT field.
- 72% of the respondents are aware of the existence of non-technical training programmes.
- According to the data most common source of information was through social media platforms, with 22% of respondents.
- According to the research, 56% of the respondents have personally participated in non-technical training programmes.
- According to the data most commonly pursued program is Communication and Presentation Skills with 25%.
- According to the research, several factors that encouraged individuals to participate in non-technical training programmes, the most significant factor is 'relevant content and topics' with 32%.

- According to the data we can say that 50% of respondents confirmed that there are costs associated with attending non-training programmes.
- According to the data, most of the respondents are extremely aware of corporate communication training programs (19%) and not aware at all about behavioral training programs (11%).
- According to the data, the most preferred format by respondents is virtual training sessions with 23%.
- 17% of the respondents highly agreed on the essentiality of non-technical training programmes for career growth in the IT industry.
- 16% of the respondents highly agree on an increase in demand for non-technological training programmes in the IT industry in Ahmedabad in recent years.
- 14% of the respondents are highly agree and 5% of the respondents are highly disagree for easily accessibility of non-technical programmes in the IT industry in Ahmedabad.
- 21% of the respondents are very confident and 1% of the respondents are not confident at all in applying the skills learned from non-technical training programmes in their daily work.
- 18% of the respondents are very satisfied with the non-technical training programmes offered by corporate trainers in the IT industry in Ahmedabad city.
- 18% of the respondents do rely on social media platforms to stay updated about non-technical programmes in the IT industry.

CONCLUSION

The major purpose of this survey was to check the awareness level of various non-technical programs. Through this survey, we can see how education industry is evolving with time. This study reveals the awareness level of various non-technical programs, most beneficial programs, platforms, preferred format, factors that encouraged individuals to participate in such programs, target audience and satisfaction level as well.

As an overall conclusion, it was very surprising that now people are shifting away from traditional teaching methods to modern teaching methods. But in this fast-moving world it is necessary to keep up with the times. Modern teaching methods are less time consuming. It is sure that this study will help the company to make it more effective. These findings will definitely give direction to the company to grow and to know where it needs to improve.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research is still needed on the topic of a study on awareness of various non-technical training programmes conducted by corporate trainers for it companies in Ahmedabad.

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